

Assessment of Mathematics Learning on Entrepreneurial Skills Development among Secondary School Students in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger State

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Abstract:

This paper discussed the assessment of mathematics learning on entrepreneurial skill development among secondary school students in Kontagora. The study revealed the importance of mathematics education in skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development. The research questions such as what is the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development and what is the mean response of students' perceptions on relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development for economic diversification and poverty reduction were developed. The hypotheses the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high. There is no significant difference in the mean response of students' perceptions in public and private schools on mathematics skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction. A survey designed was adopted for the study. The population of the study was students in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger State. A random sampling technique was used to obtain the sampled used for the work. The sample consists of 100 students. Basic Mathematics Skills Questionnaire (BMSQ) was used for data collection. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the research hypotheses were tested using t- test at 0.05 level of significant. The findings of the study show that the students agreed that mathematics provides basic skills for entrepreneurship development which in turn promotes economic development and reduce poverty. Recommendation such as the entrepreneurship education should be encouraged at all level of education among others is suggested.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Mathematics, Skills.

Introduction

In Nigeria today, unemployment has become a daily challenge. Nigeria is now facing one of the greatest threats to her existence as a nation, because of high level of unemployment, especially among the youths. This has led to poverty, banditry, kidnapping, and unrest among the unemployed people. Poverty is a global issue for both developed and underdeveloped countries. Poverty takes different forms. It can be in form of both income and non-income dimensions. To some people, poverty is a state of lacking the human basic needs such as adequate nutritious food, clothing, housing, clean water and health services, glaringly unemployment leads to poverty. In Nigeria unemployment is increasing every day. It is pertinent to know that Nigeria at 63 years of independence is still facing the problem of unemployment. Among other factors, this can be attributed to lack of basic skills in learners which could help them to venture in to entrepreneurship when they pass out from school. Also majority of the graduates from tertiary institutions who are job seekers are forced to venture into frauds of any kind. The era of depending on government for job is almost eroded, as government alone could not cater for job creation. There is no doubt that our graduates may have employment opportunities if they are adequately provided with entrepreneurial education (Olaniyan & Ezekiel, 2019). From the aforementioned there is a need to close the gap through skills acquisition because without entrepreneurial skills youth development would be hampered and this in turn would lead to poverty. Since there is population explosion, there is need to provide room for students' self-reliance and this can be done through entrepreneurship education. When students have sufficient knowledge in entrepreneurship education, it will help them to be self-employed later in future and contributes meaningfully to the society.

Mathematics provides fundamental skills for societal transformations. Today, mathematics is the language and key to every days' activities in science, technology, commerce and even art (Sadi & Haruna, 2020). Mathematics is a powerful tool

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for technological development. It solves security, poverty problems and provides necessary skills for economic diversification. Mathematics as a tool, its knowledge and skills are bedrock of all societal transformation and transfer of ideas into reality (Abubakar, Wokoma & Afebuame, 2012). Also, Malik and Salman (2018) stated that mathematics is a core subject which serves as fundamental for pupils' level of thinking, skill development and problem solving. It is interesting to know that the advancement in the areas of science and technology are indebted to mathematics to a great extent. The knowledge of mathematics is fundamental in addressing the critical issues of security problems, poverty alleviation and economic transformation. Mathematics is a core subject which serves as fundamental for learners' level of thinking, skill development and problem solving, which are fundamental for future task. It is interesting to know that the advancement in the areas of science and technology are indebted to mathematics to a great extent.

Mathematics Education is the practice of teaching and learning mathematics along with problem solving techniques and issues relating to curriculum (Ugboduma & Alio, 2014). The role of mathematics education in a nation's development cannot be over emphasized. Mathematics education improves the cognitive development of learners, which in turns gives room for reasoning, analytical and problem -solving skills acquisitions which are fundamental in the labour market and entrepreneurship development. Mathematics education provides skills that are applicable in all facets of life. According to Omole (2017) and Federal Ministry of Education. (2007), at basic level the following topics are taught: number and numeration, measurement, basic operation, geometry, algebraic processes and everyday statistics. These help to achieve objectives of teaching mathematics at this level. It includes to:

1. Acquire mathematical literacy necessary to function in an informative age.
2. Cultivate the understanding and application of mathematical skills and concepts necessary to thrive in an ever-changing technological world and
3. Develop essential elements of problem solving, communication, reasoning and connection within their study of mathematics.

Entrepreneurship Education is that aspect of education which equips an individual with the mind-set to undertake the risk of venturing into something new by applying knowledge and skill acquisition in schools (Omokaro, 2019). Dianda and Azyme (2020) says that entrepreneurship is a part of business life that contributes towards successful organization. The authors said further that business is healthy when there is entrepreneurial skills and management are adopted for changing and learning. According to Lawal et al, (2023), entrepreneurship education is seeing as an aspect of education that equips an individual with the mindset to undertake the risk of venturing into something new by applying knowledge and skills acquired in school. Entrepreneurship can be described as means of equipping the individual through skills acquisition in different vocational trades to harness investment opportunity and promote self-employment. Furthermore, entrepreneurship can be described as a process of creating something new, in different ways through the skills acquisitions for taking risk for the purpose of making profit and adding value to life. Entrepreneurship is an integral part of industrial growth, which is a backbone of any nation's development. Entrepreneurship education builds in a learner the necessary skills for self –reliance and society development. Adeagbo (2018) said that the students had positive attitude towards entrepreneurship and they were willing to be self-employed or become entrepreneur after graduation. According to Fada et al (2017), entrepreneurship education prepares students to establish career in entrepreneurship.

A nation where entrepreneurship is accorded recognition such a country will have very low unemployment rate and poverty reduction. Mathematics is a creative discipline which can be described as a huge body of knowledge which is essential for the development of entrepreneurship skills, because everywhere we go, everything we do or propose to do, either structures of mathematics or its applications play a vital role (Aliyu et al. 2017). In a related development, Adegoke (2013) stated that students develop numeracy, reasoning, thinking skills and problems solving skills through the learning and application of Mathematics. The authors added that the importance of mathematics is not limited to every science and technology but also in every living and the work place. Also, Ezech and Uqwanyyi (2013) captured a huge of career opportunities in banking, engineering, architecture, information technology, accountancy that heavily rely on mathematics principle that could generate entrepreneurship opportunities.

The philosophy of Nigeria education and the philosophy of mathematics education both aim at developing skills, competence and knowledge that could propel every individual in to entrepreneurship activities (Olaniyan & Ezekiel, 2019). The teachers play a major role in making this philosophy comes to reality. Effective teaching of mathematics must be the concern of all stakeholders to provide the prerequisite skills for the entrepreneurship activities to triumph. The situation of unemployment in the world today call for attention of all stakeholders. Every year, fresh graduates are released to job market without acquiring necessary entrepreneurial skills that can help them to live on their own and contribute to the development of

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their community. To curb this trend and to minimize overdependence on white collar job, entrepreneurship development must continue to give priority to at all level of education in the country. Therefore, this paper examines the role of teaching mathematics in the development of entrepreneurial skills among secondary school students,

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate senior secondary school students' perceptions on learning mathematics for entrepreneurship development. Specifically, the study sought to investigate the following:

1. To know students' perceptions on importance of mathematics in entrepreneurial development;
2. To compare male and female students' perceptions on importance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development;
3. To examine students' perceptions of relevance of mathematics based on intention to work after school;
4. To determine the basic mathematics skills relevant for the development of entrepreneurial skills.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for skills acquisitions for entrepreneurial development?
2. What is the mean response of students on relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development for economic diversification and poverty reduction?
3. What is the mean response of male and female students on relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development?

Hypotheses

1. H_{O1} . The mean response of students on importance of mathematics learning for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high.
2. H_{O2} . There is no significant difference in the mean response of students on importance of mathematics learning in public and private schools on skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction.
3. H_{O3} . There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female students on importance of learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was used to carry out the study. The population of the study was students in the secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area, the sample consists of 100 students drawn from SS2 and SS3 secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area, Niger state. Both private and secondary school students were used. The first section of the questionnaire was used to elicit general information on age, gender and type of schools. The second section consists of a checklist of basic mathematics skills questionnaire. The research instruments designed for data collection was a 16-items Basic Mathematics Skills Questionnaire (BMSQ) constructed by the researcher on a four -point scale of Very High (VH), High (H), Low (L), Very Low (VL) representing 4,3 ,2 and 1 respectively. The questionnaire was given to two mathematics teachers for validation. The questionnaire was administered with the help of teachers in the selected schools. The mean and standard deviation and t-test were employed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version for data analysis.

Result

Research Question 1

What is the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics for skills acquisitions for entrepreneurial development

Table 1. Mean response of importance of mathematics education in the development of entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

S/N	Items description	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	The use of mathematical skills can lead to acquisition of creative entrepreneurship skills	3.53	24.67	Accepted
2	With the help of mathematical skills, entrepreneurs are able to diversify their knowledge in their enterprises.	3.56	25.89	Accepted
3	Mathematical skills acquisition help me in everyday situations.	3.13	15.20	Accepted

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4	It helps in estimation and approximation, that is, in estimating quantity, length, distance.	3.70	31.61	Accepted
5	The knowledge of mathematics operations can provide growth in business.	3.58	25.99	Accepted
6	I understand that a good knowledge of mathematics can help an entrepreneur to analysis gains and loss in business.	3.76	32.34	Accepted
7	The mathematical skills help in reading, interpreting, constructing tables, charts and graphs.	3.40	23.22	Rejected
8	Mathematical skills help in computer literacy.	3.02	15.33	Accepted
9	The knowledge of mathematics help students to see the relationship between mathematics and business.	3.49	23.44	Accepted
10	The knowledge of mathematics is good for predictions for future events in businesses.	3.10	15.02	Accepted
11	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs In planning for poverty reduction.	3.22	17.33	Accepted
12	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for economic growth.	3.22	18.16	Accepted
13	It helps in planning for job creations	3.18	16.58	Accepted
14	The knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for employment.	3.22	18.16	Accepted
15	The mathematical skills help entrepreneurs in planning for infrastructural development.	3.19	20.89	Accepted
16	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to reduce hunger in the land.	2.64	7.77	Accepted
Total Mean Weight Average/Cluster Mean		3.31	20.72	Accepted

Table 1 shows that the mean of each items ranges from 2.64 to 3.76 are greater than 2.5 the cutoff point. Moreover, the cluster means of 3.42 was found to be above the cut-off point of 2.5. This implies that the respondents (students) perception on learning mathematics for skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development is affirmative.

Research Question 2

What is the mean response of students on the relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction?

Table 2. Mean responses on extent to which mathematics enhances entrepreneurial skills.

S/N	Items description	Private		Public		Decision
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
11	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to diversify their enterprises to reduce poverty.	3.14	3.33	3.30	8.60	Accepted
12	With the help of mathematics skills, entrepreneurs are able to diversify their knowledge in their business for economic growth.	3.08	3.40	3.22	9.35	Accepted
13	It helps entrepreneurs to diversify their knowledge in their business for job creations	3.12	3.25	3.23	8.49	Accepted
14	The knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for employment.	3.14	3.33	3.35	9.42	Accepted
15	The mathematical skills help entrepreneurs in planning for infrastructural development.	3.16	3.18	3.09	9.06	Accepted
16	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to diversify their knowledge in their business to reduce hunger in the land.	2.46	2.88	2.52	6.48	Accepted
Total Mean Weight Average/Cluster Mean		3.02	11.58	3.12	10.39	Accepted

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Based on the data presented in table 2, it was evident that all the 11-16 items were rated above 2.5

The grand mean for public school is 3.34 while that of private school is 3.33 meaning that the respondents agreed positively that mathematics skill acquisition boost entrepreneurial development. This also implies that there was no difference between the students' view in public school and that of their private school counterparts towards relevance of mathematics entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

Research Question 3.

What is the mean response of male and female students on relevance of mathematics skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development?

Table 3: Mean rating on how mathematics education provides entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

S/N	Items description	Male		Female		Decision
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	The use of mathematical skills can lead to acquisition of creative entrepreneurship skills	3.57	12.68	3.58	13.07	Accepted
2	With the help of mathematical skills, entrepreneurs are able to diversify their knowledge in their enterprises.	3.71	11.81	3.51	12.20	Accepted
3	Mathematical skills acquisition helps me in everyday situations.	3.33	9.71	3.38	10.44	Accepted
4	It helps in estimation and approximation, that is, in estimating quantity, length, distance.	3.80	17.95	3.71	12.04	Accepted
5	The knowledge of mathematics operations can provide growth in business.	3.40	11.93	3.67	14.43	Accepted
6	I understand that a good knowledge of mathematics can help an entrepreneur to analysis gains and loss in business.	3.91	19.92	3.78	16.52	Accepted
7	The mathematical skills help in reading, interpreting, constructing tables, charts and graphs.	3.27	13.35	3.33	10.31	Rejected
8	Mathematical skills help in computer literacy.	2.93	8.74	2.92	6.93	Accepted
9	The knowledge of mathematics help students to see the relationship between mathematics and business.	3.39	12.50	3.53	12.42	Accepted
10	The knowledge of mathematics is good for predictions for future events in businesses.	3.47	11.84	3.11	8.06	Accepted
11	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs In planning for poverty reduction.	3.13	7.63	3.30	9.20	Accepted
12	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for economic growth.	3.40	11.93	3.22	10.24	Accepted
13	It helps in planning for job creations	3.07	9.20	3.23	9.20	Accepted
14	The knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs in planning for employment.	3.11	9.00	3.35	10.80	Accepted
15	The mathematical skills help entrepreneurs in planning for infrastructural development.	3.17	10.75	3.09	9.81	Accepted
16	A good knowledge of mathematics helps entrepreneurs to reduce hunger in the land.	2.54	5.07	2.52	4.55	Accepted
Total Mean Weight Average/Cluster Mean		3.33	11.50	10.64	3.33	Accepted

Table three indicates that the grand mean for male students is 3.33 while that female is also 3.33. The difference in grand mean is zero. This implies that there was no difference between the male and female students' perception towards relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development.

Hypotheses Testing

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HO₁: The mean response of students on importance of mathematics learning for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high.

Table 4: t- test of students’ response on mathematics education for skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development.

Description	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Agreed	70	3.035	10.39	88	2.001	1.987	NS
Disagreed	20	0.279	10.52				

Table 4 revealed that t-calculated is greater than the t-critical. Thus, the Null Hypothesis I (H₀₁) at P<0.05 which stated that “The students’ perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is not significantly high” was rejected. However, the mean perception of students’ affirmation of 3.035 was found to be significantly greater than the mean of students’ perception depicting disapproval is 0.279. This implies that the students’ perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is high.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean response of students on importance of learning mathematics in public and private schools on skills acquisition for economic diversification and poverty reduction.

Table 5 showing t- test of students’ response on importance of mathematics skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development based on school - type

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Public School	40	3.34	10.39	88	0.0259	1.987	NS
Private School	50	3.28	11.58				

In table 5, t-calculated of 0.00259 is less than t-critical of 1.987. Hence, Hypothesis II (H₀₂) which states that “there is no significant difference between the students’ perceptions in public and private schools on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development” was accepted. However, the mean perception of public-school students of 3.34 was found to be greater than the mean of private school students’ perception of 3.28. They both agree that skills acquisition plays important role in grow of economy and poverty reduction.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female students on importance of mathematics learning for entrepreneurial development.

Table 6: t- test of male and female students’ perceptions on mathematics skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	46	3.33	11.50	88	0.001	1.987	NS
Female	44	3.31	10.64				

In table 6, t-calculated of 0.001 is less than t-critical of 1.987. Hence, Hypothesis III (H₀₃) which states that “there is no significant difference in male and female students’ perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development” was accepted. This shows that there is no gender difference in their perceptions.

Discussion of Findings

Data represented in table one shows that the students agreed that mathematics provides necessary skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development. They agreed that mathematics skills acquisition help them in daily activities. Also, the grand mean of 3.42 obtained shows that the respondent agrees to the items such as that the knowledge of mathematics helps in analyzing of profit made, reading, interpreting, constructing tables, diversifying of enterprises among others to venture into entrepreneurial career choice. The finding from the study in research question 2 revealed that there was no significant difference in the students’ perception in public and that of private schools’ counterparts towards relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development. They both agreed that mathematics plays major roles in skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development. This implies that the application of skills acquisition by entrepreneurs helps to diversify their knowledge in their business for economic growth, poverty reduction, creation of jobs among others. Entrepreneurship will boost their carrier choice as entrepreneurs which help them to solve their problems and the society. The finding was supported by Adeagbo (2018) who said that the students had positive attitude towards entrepreneurship and they were willing to be self-employed or become

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entrepreneur after graduation. Also, the study is supported by Fada et al (2017) which agreed that entrepreneurship education prepares students to establish career in entrepreneurship, Also Lawal et al (2023) agreed with the result, by saying that the *entrepreneurship education provides an experiential training for students which allow them to apply the skills acquired to establish career in entrepreneurship.*

The finding from the study in research question 3 indicated that there was no gender difference in students' perception towards relevance of mathematics for entrepreneurial development. They all viewed that mathematics skills are useful for entrepreneurial development. The result of hypotheses revealed that the students' perception on learning mathematics for entrepreneurial development is high. Also, it showed that the students were of the opinion that there is application of mathematics skills acquisition in the lives of entrepreneurs, which gives room for diversification in business endeavors.

Conclusion

It must be noted that all educational objectives are stated by the philosophy of a particular country in question. Therefore, objectives of teacher education are based on the philosophy of education in Nigeria. It is also observed that development is far from a nation that did not encourage quality entrepreneurship education, because products of such educational system cannot contribute greatly to the development of the society. Based on the findings, the students' perception on mathematical skills acquisition for entrepreneurial development is encouraging. Thus, the study concludes that the students were willing to learn mathematics for necessary skills acquisition to become entrepreneurs after their study in school, as the knowledge acquired from entrepreneurship would equip them with necessary skills and knowledge to become successful business persons and makes them to be self-reliance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made

1. The entrepreneurship education should be encouraged at all level of education
2. All stakeholders should provide enabling environments for mathematics teachers to improve mathematics education in Nigeria.
3. Students should be encouraged to show positive attitude towards the learning of mathematics

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